

THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC DIDACTIC THINKING EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH LEARNING IN STUDENTS IMPROVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In the article, learning a foreign language is related to education, science, economy, politics and considered the main key for the new era of globalization in social life are discussed, the criteria of the effectiveness of foreign language learning are given.

Globalizing education is now creating opportunities for both learners and teachers to pursue education and research around the world.

We know from the sources that in human society, people are interested in knowing several languages, they feel the need for it. Later, he was eager to learn English, French and other languages. First, he focused on the pronunciation of the words of this language, and then he studied its grammar. In fact, if you speak to people abroad in their native language, this is a deep respect for them, their country, and their history represents the symbol. In the era of globalization, when international relations are developing, learning foreign languages is considered a major political and cultural process. Our famous encyclopedic scientists wrote almost all of their scientific discoveries in Arabic.

Our compatriots Abu Nasr Farabi, Beruni, ibn Sina knew several languages perfectly. In ancient Movarounnahr, artistic creations were written in Turkish, Persian and Arabic languages. After all, it is not for nothing that it is said in our nation that "He who knows the language knows the world."

Indeed, mastering a foreign language is the main key for the new era of globalization in education, science, economy, politics and social life.

Globalizing education is now creating opportunities for both learners and educators to pursue education and research around the world. This process makes it possible for graduates of secondary vocational schools to learn various worldly knowledge in foreign languages, as well as to continue their professional knowledge in foreign languages. It is these 4 that form the basic structure of language learning based on skill. Foreign languages are taught in the form of games and oral speech lessons from the first grade of general secondary schools, and from the second grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar are gradually mastered.

will be passed.

Therefore, it is important to achieve efficiency in teaching foreign languages at a time when Uzbek youth grow up like no other, and in a time when proper conditions are created for imparting modern education. So what is meant by effectiveness in language teaching?

In particular, pupils and students learn languages other than their own in language classes while learning, while gaining some knowledge of the language they are learning they want to develop the ability to speak and write freely in that language. That is, for example, while learning Uzbek language, foreign language speakers should acquire certain knowledge of the Uzbek language in the course of their lessons and develop the skills of speaking and writing freely in this language. When the Uzbek language subject is taught to the students studying in Russian groups, usually the efficiency of the lesson (each individual lesson is taken into account) what kind of knowledge the student or student in this group has about the Uzbek language, the most important thing is how fluently they speak, how well their speech in this language has grown, and how their writing skills have improved. is determined by the fact that it forms in itself. In this respect, we know that the teacher sets himself the goal of ensuring that each lesson is effective, that is, he envisions a result and works towards achieving this result.

As we know, in our country, a continuous system of teaching foreign languages, especially English, was established in general secondary schools, as we mentioned above. At the next stage of education, attention is focused on instilling knowledge that has not been deeply mastered in the general secondary school program. Such cases have been observed in practice: an attempt is made to teach a student Russian or another language for several years in general secondary schools. Based on the program, teachers tried to teach these languages continuously in the classroom. According to the plan, the lessons were completed, various activities were conducted. However, most of the pupils or students in the group eventually graduate without the ability to speak or write the language fluently. But in the process of live communication, which is made by the situation, they will master this language within a year - they will be able to speak it freely. We witnessed another case. One year, fifteen Kazakh girls studied in one group. When dictation was taken from them in the form of written work, they completed the task with excellent marks. Also, the girls of this group were able to write a dictation in Russian with excellent marks. The main attention is directed to the correct pronunciation of words, phrases, sentences. After two or three months, the student learns the language in such a way that he can speak Uzbek fluently and get good grades. Aspirations begin to bear positive results.

Since independence, representatives of other nations living in Uzbekistan, including Russians, have been consciously developing the ability to speak Uzbek to a certain extent in the process of communicating with Uzbeks in neighborhoods, streets, and workplaces. So, the point is that it becomes clear that the result will be as expected only when the goal is to achieve the effectiveness of teaching in the lessons in the educational process. It is self-evident that there are various ways and means of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson in the educational process, including in Russian groups or in teaching other foreigners to speak or write in the Uzbek language, and each teacher tries to use these opportunities based on his ability. The teacher has aspirations to use different methods of teaching, he uses different

modern teaching methods. All of these are good. However the effect is not the same, nor can it be the same. Because the teachers are different, the conditions are different, the opportunities are different, the interests are different, the responsibility for teaching and learning the language is different, and the approach is different.

Improving efficiency in the educational system requires a lot of skills, knowledge, experience and other things from the teacher. It is even useful to fully feel that today's knowledge, skills, experience, tools, opportunities, teaching methods and methods of the teacher may not be effective tomorrow or for the students of this group. Therefore, the first main factor of increasing teaching efficiency is related to the teacher's work on himself, increasing his opportunities to feel responsibility, correctly defining the goal and what the result will be. Everyone knows this, but it doesn't hurt to point it out. Because not everyone fully and correctly feels that the effectiveness of the teaching system has a lot to do with the teacher's professional activity. In this case, the knowledge of the teacher will not be enough. Perhaps even years of experience will not work. In language teaching, it is probably very important to take into account the skill, observation, sensitivity of the teacher, the fact that there are specific aspects of language teaching, the independent activity of the student to learn the language, and the fact that this activity is combined with the teacher's activity. The work of a teacher who understands this can really claim the first factor in language teaching. The second factor is, of course, inextricably linked with the first, and in our opinion, it is the formation of respect, affection, enthusiasm, and interest in the subject or field being taught in students.

When a student learns another language, he should develop love and respect for this language. If passion, passion, and interest are not awakened, the student's language learning will be in trouble, just like a greyhound tied around the neck is not suitable for hunting. It goes without saying that lust requires the next factor. That is, it is necessary to highlight the possibilities of using language units in speech more during the course of the lesson, and to familiarize the pupils and students with these possibilities. For this, it is necessary to organize the teaching process in a live communication style as much as possible. Such a lesson process can be organized informally in two ways:

- 1) student-student interaction (live conversation);
- 2) in the forms of live communication (live conversation) of pupils-students-teacher.

The next lesson can be conducted in the form of a one-on-one conversation between the teacher and students or a general conversation. In the course of the conversation, the pupil-student is taught to speak live - to communicate. It is taught that one concept or idea can be expressed through different words or sentences, combinations, and to use language units in practice. But for this situation, students must be aware of important academic vocabulary. It is said that their effective use in the course of the lesson and outside of the lesson is of great importance in language learning.

We know that our people have been multilingual in many regions of Uzbekistan for centuries. Uzbek-Tajik bilingualism is currently practiced in Ferghana Valley, Bukhara, Samarkand oases and many other places. Trilingualism also prevailed in these regions (the people of these regions could easily communicate in Uzbek, Tajik, and Russian languages). Many people of our country communicate easily in four languages. That is, there were those

who learned Arabic or another language. Uzbeks belong to the Turkic-speaking peoples, have received the status of a separate literary language and interacted with representatives of languages such as Uyghur, Turkish, Azerbaijani, Tatar, Turkmen, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, and Karachoi.

Nowadays, especially young people are encouraged to learn other languages, but this does not mean reducing the attention to the mother tongue. Therefore, in addition to learning a foreign language, teaching the Uzbek language, forming the skills of writing and speaking in Uzbek in an exemplary manner in both young people and adults, and bringing them to adulthood so that they can speak in a cultural way, serves as a bridge in raising them to become perfect human beings.

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